

COST ACTION 'PROBE' VIRTUAL MOBILITY REPORT by Annachiara Bellini
(1, 2, 3)

Overview of the current methodologies for the retrieval of aerosol extinction and mass concentration profiles from Automated Lidar-Ceilometers

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1. Rationale

The retrieval of aerosol optical and physical properties from Automated-Lidar Ceilometers (ALCs) has become increasingly important thanks to the spreading of ALC networks and their capacity to provide operationally quantitative aerosol information to the scientific and stakeholder communities. ALC-based products include, among others, aerosol backscatter, extinction, and mass concentration profiles, directly usable by the research community as well as by environmental, meteorological, health and aviation safety agencies. The foreseen employment of depolarization profiles (e.g., Gobbi et al., 2002; Ansmann et al., 2011) is also a promising strategy to exploit capabilities of Automated Polarization-sensitive Lidar Ceilometers (APLC, e.g., Gobbi et al., 2019).

The inversion of the ALC raw signal into aerosol backscatter, extinction, and mass concentration profiles requires calibration and signal-correction procedures as well as specific inversion algorithms. Different European research groups and institutions autonomously developed methodologies to derive these key aerosol properties.

However, these methodologies may have significantly different approaches. For example, some are based on model-derived functional relationships among variables (e.g., Dionisi et al, 2018), some on specific conversion factors and ancillary data (e.g., Mortier et al., 2013).

In the frame of a Virtual Management Grant of the PROBE Cost Action (<https://www.probe-cost.eu>), a review of the different approaches for the ALC-based aerosol retrievals has been performed and is summarized in this document. It analyses the approaches currently applied within the European ALC networks in Italy (ALICENET), UK (MetOffice), Norway (V-PROFILE) and France (ACTRIS-AERIS). This outcome is thought to be useful not only for the Cost Action PROBE, but also for other European initiatives, such as E-PROFILE (<https://e-profile.eu>) and the EC H2020 project RI-URBANS (<https://riurbans.eu/>).

2. Contributing networks

The collaboration involved different European research groups and Institutions dealing with aerosol retrievals from remote sensing observations as listed above. Some preliminary information on these networks and relevant processing line is given hereafter.

Network (country)	processing	Input data
ALICENET (IT)	at CNR-ISAC (https://www.alice-net.eu/)	E-PROFILE L2 data for CHM15k, adapted netCDF for CL61

Met Office (UK)	on Lidarnet and DRIVE WebApp (both Met Office internal) for Raymetrics, CL61 and CHM15k. A-Profiles processing for CL61, CHM15k (and CL31)	E-PROFILE L2 data for CHM15k (and CL31), adapted netCDF for CL61 and sun-photometer (where available), Raw Raymetrics data.
V/A-Profiles (NO, EU)	A-Profiles processing (open-source, available on Git https://github.com/AugustinMortier/A-Profiles)	E-PROFILE L2 data (netCDF)
ACTRIS-AERIS (FR)	BASIC-evolution processing (https://www.icare.univ-lille.fr/basic/)	backscattered signal L2 data, sun-photometer data, in-situ data (nephelometer and aethalometer).
DWD (DE)	Operative algorithm (python, self-made)*	CHM15k raw data, output of old E-PROFILE calibration code operated at DWD

* Possible future contributions will be inserted in an updated document

3. Methods

The review is organized accordingly to the main steps required for the retrieval of aerosol backscatter, extinction, and mass concentration profiles from ALCs, i.e., 1) signal correction and calibration procedures, 2) aerosol backscatter and extinction calculations, 3) aerosol mass concentration retrievals.

The procedures applied within each network processing line for each step are described (methods and assumptions, sources of uncertainty and expected accuracy of the products, status of implementation and settings, instrumental requirements, processed and potentially available datasets). A summarizing Table is reported in the Appendix.

3.1 Signal correction and calibration

Prior to the application of calibration and inversion procedures, the overlap correction of the ALC signal is needed to obtain reliable aerosol profiles near the surface and transmission values along the column. The calibration is then required to obtain absolute backscatter profiles and to extract homogeneous information from ALC networks.

3.1.1 ALICENET

The overlap correction applied to CHM15k systems is based on the procedure of Hervo et al. (2016). This includes the automatic retrieval of homogeneous aerosol layers and correspondent overlap daily corrections, followed by the derivation of an overlap model from an ensemble of daily corrections (seasonal/temperature-dependent). As the assumption of ground-based homogeneous aerosol layers is not always appropriate (e.g., elevated aerosol advections, hygroscopic effects), a specific filter is applied on the ensemble requiring a non-increasing difference between overlap daily-corrected and standard profiles over rolling windows of 4-5 days, and only daytime-derived corrections. The results have been evaluated using AERONET products and near molecular atmosphere profiles.

The automatic Rayleigh calibration applied to CHM15k systems includes:

1) the search of the molecular zone. The signal is averaged over 3-6 hours every clear night, a minimum SNR is required between 3-7 km, and a rolling window routine is used to find the best fit between real and synthetic profiles. Different quality controls are performed (Breusch-Godfrey test and cumulative sign in residuals) to filter elevated aerosol layers;

2) the backward Klett inversion of the lidar equation is used, with an iterative technique and variable LR profiles (derived using a polynomial function linking aerosol extinction to aerosol backscatter, see next section). Final quality controls on the calibration constant (CL) uncertainty and integrated extinction are also performed.

The main assumptions of this procedure are: a calibration window with only molecular backscatter, a molecular profile from Bodhaine's formulation and standard atmosphere, the polynomial coefficients of the backscatter-to-extinction relationship, the first-guess LR value within the iterative procedure. These assumptions (and the SNR in the calibration zone) are the main sources of systematic (random) errors. The results are site-dependent CL time series with a (generally observed) seasonal cycle of $\pm 15\%$. The reasons of this seasonal variability are currently under investigation. The procedure is potentially operative in NRT (with either fixed or variable LR). At present, the database of five ALICENET CHM15k systems have been processed using variable LR and bounded/smoothed CL timeseries to derive aerosol products. The procedure has also been tested with a CL61 operating in ALICENET, producing calibration coefficients close to 1 (their stability will be assessed in the next months).

3.1.2 Met Office

The overlap correction provided by the factory is applied to ALC systems.

For CHM15k, a Rayleigh calibration is performed in clear nights, using the inwards Klett with fixed LR. The molecular profile is calculated using either standard atmosphere or radiosonde data. The main assumptions are a clear calibration height with only molecular backscatter, the LR value representative of the aerosol present in the boundary layer. The sources of uncertainty are the molecular profile, the residual aerosol at reference range, the LR value. For CL61, the factory calibration is used at the moment. The procedure is manual for CHM15K (with plans to automate) and CL31 (only on test basis), and automated on internal R&D server for Raymetrics LR111-300 and CL61.

3.1.3 V/A-Profiles

The information on the procedure for overlap correction is not available at the moment.

For CHM15k and CL instruments, the Level 2 data are calibrated. The calibration coefficient from E-PROFILE (median value) is used and the uncertainty is estimated using the seasonal variability. Mini-MPL measurements have shown large variability in the calibration coefficients. The backward Klett inversion is thus used to derive aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles (see next section).

3.1.4 ACTRIS-AERIS

The information on the procedure for overlap correction is not available at the moment.

The backward Klett inversion is currently applied to retrieve aerosol products (see next section). The main perspective within the network is the derivation of corrections and calibrations for Cimel, mini-MPL, and Campbell sensors.

3.1.5 Summary of used signal correction and calibration procedures

Overlap correction procedures are based on the factory-provided correction curves, the comparison with climatological reference profiles, or the application of a site-dependent overlap model.

The applied calibration procedure depends on the stability and noise level of the ALC system. For CHM15k and systems with a sufficient SNR above 5 km, a Rayleigh calibration is generally applied. The implementations mainly differ in the search of the molecular zone, in the extinction calculation, and in the quality controls to filter aerosol layers in the calibration window. Overall, the major uncertainty in the derived calibration coefficients relates to the observed seasonal variability resulting in most sites. At present, smoothed/median values are operationally used within the networks. For Vaisala CL systems, a liquid cloud calibration is generally performed; for CL61, the factory calibration is currently used. For mini-MPL, a backward Klett inversion is directly applied to obtain aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles and the calibration is currently under investigation. The backward method does not need a calibration coefficient, but is very sensitive to the LR profile in the lower part of the troposphere, and to background signal, noise level, and residual aerosol at the reference altitude (Wiegner and Geiß, 2014). These effects are particularly evident during extreme aerosol events (e.g., Diémoz et al., 2020).

3.2 Aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles

The inversion of the ALC signal into aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles can be performed once a full overlap of the instrument laser beam and field-of-view down to the surface has been obtained and a good calibration has been performed. Further requirements are a sufficient SNR up to at least 7 km for the detection of long-range transported tropospheric aerosol, a sufficiently high vertical and temporal resolution to follow rapid aerosol and cloud dynamics, and an operational wavelength out of major atmospheric gases absorption bands to avoid need of further corrections.

The different approaches employed to this aim are described hereafter, specifying for each network: 1) methodology and assumptions, 2) sources of uncertainty and expected accuracy of the products, 3) status of implementation and settings of the processing line, 4) instrumental requirements, 5) processed and potentially available datasets and 6) perspectives.

3.2.1 ALICENET

The retrieval of aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles in ALICENET is based on the forward Klett inversion with variable lidar ratios (LR). These latter are obtained using polynomial functions linking aerosol backscatter to aerosol extinction as described in Dionisi et al. (2018), and an iterative technique until convergence of the backscatter profile. In brief, the functional relationships are derived as 'mean' behavior of a large set (thousands) of aerosol simulations performed following a Monte Carlo approach (i.e., bulk aerosol properties are derived using Mie theory with input aerosol microphysical parameters randomly chosen within specific ranges, representative of continental aerosol conditions; Barnaba and Gobbi, 2001; Dionisi et al., 2018). As a result, functional relationships linking aerosol extinction, surface area, and volume to aerosol backscatter are derived (seventh-order polynomial fit have been chosen for this purpose).

The parameters assumed in the inversion calculations are therefore the polynomial coefficients, the first-guess LR value (operatively a value $LR = 38$ sr is

used, compatible with CALIPSO at 1064 nm, Omar et al., 2009), and the molecular profile.

The main sources of uncertainty of the products are the calibration coefficients, the first-guess LR value, the polynomial coefficients, the SNR, the molecular profile. The expected accuracy for aerosol extinction profiles is 30-40% (evaluated using AERONET products), and better for backscatter profiles.

The procedure is automated and potentially operative in NRT (setting the calculation mode, i.e. iterative technique with variable LR or fixed LR, the first-guess or constant LR value, the SNR threshold).

The retrieval is based solely on ALC data (no ancillary information is used) and has been tested and evaluated for inversion of CHM15k ALC systems (Diémoz et al., 2019 a, b). At present, five ALICENET sites have been processed (four of which with 7-year database) using the iterative technique with variable LR profiles, and six datasets are potentially available for the processing.

At present, range corrected signals (RCS) are provided in NRT on the ALICENET website. The main future perspectives within the network are a NRT processing for all ALICENET sites, the derivation of the functional relationships for other aerosol types and lidar wavelengths (355, 532, 1064 nm), and the use/inversion of the polarization information in the retrieval (e.g. from CL61). In fact, ALICENET runs the first ever Polarization-sensitive ALC prototyped by Lufft (former Jenoptik) within the LIFE Project DIAPASON (Gobbi et al., 2019).

3.2.2 Met Office

The retrieval of aerosol backscatter profiles is based on the forward Klett for both CHM15k and CL61, using fixed LR appropriate for the aerosol type suspected to be present (literature values or Lidarnet measurements). If sunphotometer is available, then LR is iterated until integrated extinction matches sunphotometer AOD. The assumed parameters are the LR and the molecular profile.

For CL61, separation of backscatter profiles for spherical and irregular aerosols is derived from depolarization profiles using the methodology of Tesche et al. (2009). The assumed spherical and non-spherical particle depolarization ratios are case-dependent (literature values, or default to dust = 26%, ash = 30%, sulphate = 1% at 355nm and 910nm).

The main sources of uncertainty are the LR value, the molecular profile, and for CL61 the depolarisation ratios. The expected accuracy depends on the route (Raman + elastic / elastic only / assumed LR): exploiting Raman channels the accuracy is 20% (Ansmann et al., 2011; Osborne et al., 2018), whereas using only elastic channel and assumed LR is worse.

The procedure is manual for CHM15k and automated for CL61 (with fixed LR=50 sr). Non-operational, but visualized and made available for meteorologists (Osborne et al., 2022).

The retrieval has been applied on Raymetrics LR111-300, CHM15k, and CL61 systems; CL31 only on test basis (under investigation). The available dataset covers 10 years at 42 sites across UK.

The main future perspective is the operational and NRT implementation of the procedure.

3.2.3 V/A-Profiles

The retrieval of aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles is based on BASIC (Mortier et al., 2013; Mortier et al., 2016). At present, the forward/backward inversion is applied (depending on ceilometer calibration robustness) using assumed LR values for different pre-defined aerosol type scenarios. The main parameters in the calculation are the LR, the molecular profile, and with

backward method the assumed backscatter at the reference altitude where the inversion procedure starts.

The main sources of uncertainty are the LR value, the SNR, and the molecular profile. With backward method, the assumed backscatter at the reference altitude is an important source of uncertainty. The aerosol extinction expected accuracy is 15-20% using sunphotometer data and an appropriate 2-layers LR profile (Mortier et al., 2013), and greater using a uniform LR.

The procedure is operative in NRT, with the possibility to adjust LR profiles.

The retrieval is currently tested with CHM15k, CL61, and Mini-MPL systems; CL51/31 to be investigated. The NRT processing is applied on 2 Norwegian ceilometers since 2014 (4 and 6 since 2020 and 2021, respectively), and on about 100 instruments (Mini-MPL, CHM15k systems from E-PROFILE) since the beginning of the year 2022.

The main perspectives are the synergy with sunphotometer when available (AOD constrain), and the use of seasonal LR climatologies for best guess in automated mode.

3.2.4 ACTRIS-AERIS

The backward Klett inversion constrained with photometer data (AOD L1.5) is applied to retrieve aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles. The extinction coefficients in the blind zone are derived from in-situ measurements (nephelometer plus aethalometer). The implementation is an evolution of the BASIC algorithm (Mortier et al., 2013). Two inversion modes are currently available, differing in the measurements set as input:

1) BALIA (BASIC + Lidar + AERONET) mode: the algorithm needs naively lidar profile and AOD measurements to retrieve the extinction profile and the lidar ratio;

2) BALI (BASIC + Lidar) mode: the algorithm can perform even if only the lidar profile is available. It needs assumptions about the lidar ratio over the time range.

The main sources of uncertainty in the retrieval are the unknown LR vertical variations, and the uncertainty on the lidar signal at the reference altitude. The expected accuracy of aerosol extinction profiles is 15-25% with BALIA mode (Popovici et al., 2018).

The procedure is expected to be operative in NRT before the end of 2022 (final test running).

The main perspective is the application of calibrations for Cimel, mini-MPL, and Campbell sensors.

3.2.5 Summary of used aerosol backscatter and extinction retrievals

The retrieval of aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles is generally based on the forward Klett inversion for CHM15k and CL systems. In some networks, a backward method is used depending on ALC calibration robustness. The forward procedures applied within the networks differ primarily for the derivation of aerosol extinction and LR profiles (options are: an iterative technique involving a model-derived functional relationship, use of a fixed LR dependent on the aerosol type assumed and/or constrained with AOD data when available). These approaches involve different assumptions in their derivation and operational implementation. The overall uncertainty of the products is between 15-30%, depending on the aerosol composition and vertical distribution.

3.3 Aerosol mass concentration profiles

3.3.1 ALICENET

The retrieval of the aerosol mass profiles is based on a polynomial function linking the aerosol volume to the previously retrieved aerosol backscatter, and on assumed aerosol density profiles (uniform or vertically variable) to calculate aerosol mass concentrations.

The main sources of uncertainty are the assumed particle density, the polynomial coefficients, and the accuracy of aerosol backscatter profiles (including the molecular profile). The expected accuracy for aerosol mass concentration profiles is 50% (evaluated with in-situ data from both long-term observations and field campaigns), depending on the application (long/short-term) and aerosol situation.

The procedure is automated and potentially operative in NRT. The configuration allows a user-defined setting of particle density profiles. The retrieval is based solely on ALC data (no ancillary data required). It has been tested and evaluated with CHM15k systems (i.e., ALC wavelength 1064 nm). At present, five ALICENET sites have been processed (four with 7-year database, processed with constant density profiles for long-term evaluations), and datasets for six CHM15k systems are potentially ready to be processed.

The main future perspectives within the network are a NRT processing for all ALICENET sites, the derivation of the functional relationships for other aerosol conditions and lidar wavelengths, and the synergy with CL61 depolarization profiles (variable density profiles, calculation of fine and coarse mode mass concentrations).

3.3.2 Met Office

The retrieval of aerosol mass profiles makes use of a specific extinction derived from sunphotometer data and T-matrix calculations to derive AOD at 910 or 1064 nm for fine-spherical particles (and for coarse-irregular particles by subtracting from total AOD) plus assumed aerosol density, and of aerosol extinction profiles. The extinction profiles for coarse-irregular aerosols are used to obtain an estimate of the corresponding mass concentrations. The methodology is adapted from the established technique of Ansmann et al. (2011) and assumes that all coarse mode aerosols are irregular. Other assumptions are that the AERONET Volume Size Distribution (VSD) is accurate, and aerosol optical and physical properties (assumed spherical and non-spherical particle densities are literature values, or 2.5 g cm⁻³ for ash and dust, 1.5 g cm⁻³ for sulfate).

The main sources of uncertainty are the assumed aerosol density, the AERONET VSD and refractive index, and the accuracy of aerosol extinction profiles (including the LR and the molecular profile). The expected accuracy is 50% for Raman plus sunphotometer retrieval with well determined aerosol types; for other routes can be over 100%, depending on the difference between the modeled and the real situation (e.g., presence of coarse but relatively regular particles, elevated aerosol layers not captured by ALCs).

The procedure is manual, i.e., non-operational but visualized and made available for meteorologists.

The retrieval has been tested using CHM15k and CL61 systems plus sunphotometers.

The main future perspective is the operational implementation of the procedure for NRT availability to London VAAC meteorologists and comparison with NAME output in the event of volcanic eruptions.

3.3.3 V/A-Profiles

The retrieval of aerosol mass profiles is based on a mass extinction efficiency derived from Mie calculations and assumed aerosol optical (complex refractive

index) and microphysical (volume size distribution and density) properties for different pre-defined aerosol scenarios, and on the previously derived aerosol extinction profiles.

The main sources of uncertainty in the retrieval are the assumed aerosol optical and microphysical properties, and the accuracy of aerosol extinction profiles (including the assumed LR and the molecular profile). The expected accuracy of the product is 50-60% depending on the situation to be modeled and the SNR of the instrument.

The procedure is operative in NRT with the possibility to set aerosol scenarios online, and to adjust aerosol properties offline thanks to the integration of a Mie code in A-Profiles.

The retrieval is currently tested with CHM15k, CL61, and Mini-MPL systems; CL51/31 to be investigated. The NRT processing is applied on 2 Norwegian ceilometers since 2014 (4 and 6 since 2020 and 2021, respectively), and on about 100 instruments (Mini-MPL, CHM15k systems from E-PROFILE) since the beginning of the year 2022.

The main perspective is the synergic use of ALC and sunphotometer data when available.

3.3.4 ACTRIS-AERIS

The retrieval of aerosol mass concentration profiles makes use of a mass extinction efficiency derived from photometer inversion (AERONET complex refractive index and volume size distribution L1.5) and Mie code plus assumed aerosol density, and of the previously derived aerosol extinction profiles.

The main sources of uncertainty in the retrieval are the aerosol density, and the accuracy of both ALC (aerosol extinction profiles, derived from backward method plus photometer AOD) and photometer (refractive index and volume size distribution) inversions. The expected accuracy of aerosol mass concentration profiles is 40% (Popovici et al., 2018), depending on the aerosol situation.

The procedure is expected to be operative in NRT before the end of 2022 (final test running).

The main perspective within the network is the application of calibrations for Cimel, mini-MPL, and Campbell sensors.

3.3.5 Summary of used aerosol mass concentration retrievals

The retrieval of aerosol mass concentration profiles structurally differ between the networks. The methodology can be based on model-derived functional relationships linking aerosol volume to aerosol backscatter plus assumed aerosol density profiles, or on specific conversion factors derived from photometer data and/or assumed aerosol optical and microphysical properties in different aerosol scenarios and Mie/T-matrix calculations linking aerosol mass to aerosol extinction. When available, depolarization profiles can be used to separate spherical and non-spherical aerosol profiles (or fine and coarse particles). Each methodology involves different assumptions and parameters, and each setting has specific degrees of freedom. The different approaches have specific strengths, depending on the application (e.g., long-term assessments or analysis of specific aerosol events), the aerosol characteristics under investigation (vertical distribution and composition), the instrumental requirements (ALC-based or need of photometer/depolarization observations), and their possible generalization to different aerosol types and ALC instruments. At present, the overall uncertainty is 40-60% for all implementations, depending on the aerosol situation and the application. A common perspective is the exploitation of the

synergies with other remote sensing observations (e.g., depolarization profiles, photometer data).

4. Conclusions

The aerosol retrievals applied within the EU contributing ALC networks can differ in the formulation and instrumental requirements (regarding ALCs: CHM15k, CL61, and miniMPL currently tested, CL51/31 to be investigated). Each approach has specific advantages and limitations. ALC-based routes are suitable for large network applications (taking into account the uncertainty in their assumptions), whereas the exploitation of other remote sensing observations allows a more complete aerosol characterization (taking into account all instrumental uncertainties and the assumptions in combining the different information). Mean functional relationships allow both long and short-term analyses, whereas the choice between different aerosol scenarios can be convenient when the aerosol characteristics are known. A promising strategy to combine the ALC profiles and the sunphotometer columnar information is the use of depolarization profiles, recently available within ALC networks.

RI-URBANS (<https://riurbans.eu/>) represent a good framework to compare the aerosol retrievals from ALCs operating in selected pilot sites, particularly where co-located with advanced in-situ/remote profiling observations. E-PROFILE (<https://e-profile.eu/>) can be a good framework to apply the developed tools at European scale.

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APPENDIX

	ALICENET	Met Office	A\V-Profiles suite	AERIS	DWD
Processing line general information	ALICENET processing line, centralized at CNR-ISAC, https://www.alicenet.eu/	Processing on Lidarnet and DRIVE WebApp (both Met office internal) for Raymetrics, CL61 and CHM15K A-Profiles for CL61, CHM15k and CL31	A-Profiles (data processing) V-Profiles (visualization)	BASIC code, https://www.icare.univ-lille	Operative algorithm for ALCs, the code is python (self-made). backscatter profiles are distributed to the public on request, estimated mass profiles are used only internally in case of volcanic ash events. see
Input data	E-PROFILE level 2 data for CHM15k (netcdf), netcdf files CL61	E-profile L2 data for CHM15K (and CL31), adapted netcdf from CL61 and sun-photometer where available, Raw Raymetrics data	E-PROFILE level 2 data (netCDF)	Backscattered signal L2 data + photometer data (aeronet AOD L1.5, VSD L1.5) + in situ data (nephelometer and aethalometer)	CHM15k 24h-files (Raw data), output of old E-PROFILE calibration code (MATLAB) operated at DWD

Pre-processing	Overlap correction (Hervo et al., 2016)	None. Remarks made mainly apply to Met Office internal retrieval		Overlap, range corrected signals	overlap correction as provided by manufacturer; averaging over 1-h slices; vertical smoothing (150m), cloud screening
Calibration	Rayleigh calibration. Search of the molecular zone + backward Klett with fixed LR/iterative procedure with variable LR and Dionisi's polynomial + quality controls (see extended table). Assumptions: clear calibration window, molecular profile with Bodhaine and STA, Dionisi's polynomial, starting LR. Sources of uncertainty: molecular profile, residual aerosol, LR, SNR. Expected accuracy: 15%. Automated. Possible to set: fixed	CL61: Factory calibration only at the moment. CHM15k: Rayleigh calibration using clear nights. Inwards Klett used with fixed LR. Molecular profile using either standard atmosphere or radio sonde data. For A-profile the calibration constant from e-profile (median value) is used and uncertainty estimated using the seasonal variability. Assumptions: clear calibration height with only molecular backscatter, LR used is representative of aerosol present in the boundary layer. Sources of uncertainty: molecular	For CHM15k and CL instruments, the level 2 data are calibrated. Mini-MPL measurements have shown large variability in the calibration coefficient. Thus, a different inversion method is used for the aerosol retrievals (see backscatter and extinction).		E-PROFILE MATLAB algorithm by M. Hervo using temperature and pressure profiles from GFS. time series of lidar constants are averaged and screened for outliers.

	<p>LR/iterative procedure with variable LR. Potentially operative in NRT, previous database processed with smoothed cycle. Used instruments: CHM15k, CL61</p>	<p>profile, residual aerosol at reference range, LR. Manual at the moment for CHM15K. Plans to automate, but no time scale at the moment. Automated on internal R&D server for Raymetrics and CL61. Used instruments: Raymetrics LR111-300, CHM15k, CL61 and CL31 (only on test basis)</p>			
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Aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles

Method					
	<p>Backscatter: forward Klett, iterative procedure with variable LR and Dionisi's polynomial linking aerosol extinction to aerosol backscatter to derive the extinction, the LR profile, and finally the backscatter. Extinction: fixed LR/iterative procedure with variable LR and Dionisi's polynomial.</p>	<p>Backscatter: forward Klett for both CHM15k and CL61 using fixed LR appropriate for the aerosol type suspected to be present, unless sun-photometer (SP) data is available, then LR is iterated until integrated extinction matches SP AOD. For CL61 separation of backscatter profiles for spherical and irregular aerosols. The values of</p>	<p>Backward/Forward method (depending on ceilometer calibration robustness), using assumed LR</p>	<p>Klett backward inversion constrained with AOD from photometer measurements. Extinction coefficients in the blind zone derived from in situ measurements</p>	<p>backscatter: iterative method with fixed LR. extinction and mass profiles are estimated using conversion factors from literature or manually provided values for the individual event. The molecular profile is standard atmosphere adjusted to ground temperature</p>

		<p>the assumed spherical and non-spherical particle depolarization ratios are case dependent.</p> <p>Literature values used were available or default to</p> <p>Dust = 26%</p> <p>Ash = 30%</p> <p>Sulphate = 1%</p> <p>at 355nm and 910nm.</p> <p>No extinction product currently calculated using ALCs at the Met Office (other than the trivial conversion of backscatter profiles with an assumed LR).</p>			
Assumptions	Molecular profile, polynomial coefficients, starting LR (38 sr suggested).	Molecular profile, lidar ratio.	Molecular profile (T, P), LR	Molecular profile (T, P)	lidar ratio, standard atmosphere
Results-sources of uncertainty, expected	<p>CL variability, SNR, molecular profile, LR, polynomial coefficients</p> <p>30% for aerosol extinction</p>	<p>Molecular profile, LR values. For CL61 - depolarisation ratios</p> <p>Expected accuracy (15-20% from Ansmann et al., 2010). Depending on the route (Raman + elastic / elastic only / assumed LR)</p>	Aerosol backscatter and extinction profiles. SNR, LR, molecular profile	unknown LR vertical variations, uncertainty on the lidar signal at the ref altitude 15-25%	LR assumption, standard atmosphere, uncertainty of calibration. data with signal-to-noise ratios < 1 are omitted

accuracy		we would hope for 20% as per Ansmann, but given the uncertainty of assumed LRs could be worse.			
Status of implementation, settings	Automated. Possible to set: fixed LR/iterative procedure with variable LR, starting LR. Potentially operative in NRT, previous databases processed with variable LR.	Manual for CHM15k. Automated for CL61 with fixed LR = 50sr. Non-operational, but visualized and made available for meteorologists	Operative in NRT Possibility to adjust LR in V-Profiles	Final test, expected to be operative in NRT before the end of 2022	automated. manual operation with adjusted parameters is possible
Instrumental requirements, used instruments	Instrumental requirements: accurate overlap correction, sufficient SNR up to 7 km. Used instruments: CHM15k	Used instruments: Raymetrics LR111-300, CHM15k, CL61 and CL31 (only on test basis, not working properly yet)	Mini-MPL, CHM15k CL61 currently tested CL51/31 to be investigated		only CHM15k, firmware > 0.7
Aerosol mass concentration profiles					
Method	Use of polynomial function linking aerosol volume to aerosol backscatter	Specific extinction values calculated using aeronet data and t-matrix calculations for spherical	Use optical and microphysical properties with Mie code to calculate efficiency to	MEE computed using VSD and refractive indices from sun photometer	conversion factors from literature for first guess and automated operations. values

	<p>plus aerosol density (constant or vertically variable)</p> <p>**At the moment only tested at the ALC wavelength 1064 nm (i.e. CHM15k)</p>	<p>particles only.</p> <p>For CL61, separate backsatter profiles for spherical and non-spherical aerosols are used.</p> <p>Spherical and non-spherical particle densities: literature values where available, or: Ash and dust around 2.5 g/cm³ and 1.5 g/cm³ for sulfate</p> <p>Literature values for LR on case by case basis - often also drawing on our own measurements.</p>	<p>calculate number concentration, and density for estimating mass concentration</p>	<p>inversion and extinction efficiency from Mie code. Mass profiles retrieved using MEE and aerosol extinction profiles.</p>	<p>adjustable for specific case studies.</p>
Assumptions	<p>particle density (constant or profile), polynomial coefficients</p>	<p>Optical properties, that Aeronet size distribution is accurate. That all coarse mode aerosols are non-spherical</p>	<p>Optical and microphysical properties (VSD, mr, mi) and density</p>		<p>conversion factors (which include an assumption on aerosol type)</p>
Results-sources	<p>molecular profile, CL variability, SNR, mean aerosol type (through</p>	<p>LR, molecular profile, size distribution, refractive</p>	<p>SNR, LR, molecular profile, size distribution,</p>		<p>all assumptions are provided with an uncertainty that</p>

<p>of uncertainty, expected accuracy</p>	<p>polynomial coefficients), particle density. 45-50%</p>	<p>index, density Expected accuracy: Best we hope for is +/- 50% (for Raman retrievals + sunphotometer derived specific extinction values and well determined aerosol types). For other routes can be over 100%. Specific extinction is probably the main source of error - this will come from discrepancies between the modeling used to calculate it and the physical situation (e.g., elevated layers not captured by ALCs, coarse but 'spherical' particles)</p>	<p>refractive index, density</p>		<p>propagates to the uncertainty of the result</p>
<p>Status of implementation, settings</p>	<p>Automated. Possible to set: aerosol density profile. Potentially operative in NRT, previous databases processed with constant density profile.</p>	<p>Manual, desire to implement operationally and in NRT</p>	<p>Operative in NRT Automated for predefined aerosol types scenarios. Possibility to adjust aerosol properties manually thanks to the integration of a Mie code in A-Profiles. Possibility to select</p>	<p>Final test, expected to be operative in NRT before the end of 2022</p>	<p>automated operation with standard assumptions. manual operation with specific settings is possible</p>

			aerosol type in V-Profiles		
Instrumental requirements, used instruments	Used instruments: CHM15k	CHM15k, CL61, sun-photometer	Mini-MPL, CHM15k CL61 currently tested CL51/31 to be investigated		CHM15k, firmware > 0.7
Perspectives	Correct treatment of CL variability, NRT processing for all ALICENET sites, derivation of the functional relationships for other wavelengths (present: 355, 532, 1064 nm) and different mean aerosol conditions (present: mean continental aerosols), synergy with depolarization profiles	Desire to implement operationally and in NRT Data is visualized for use by meteorologists, i.e., available in NRT to London VAAC meteorologists, and comparison with NAME output in the event of volcanic eruptions.	Synergy with sunphotometer data when available (AOD constrain) Use of seasonal LR climatologies for best guess in automated mode	Corrections and calibrations for Cimel, miniMPL, Campbell sensors	improve cloud screening, use of molecular profile from model data
Processed dataset, potential	5 ALICENET sites processed (4 with 6-year database).	10 years plus at 42 sites across UK	2 Norwegian ceilometers in NRT since 2014 (4, and 6 since 2020 and 2021 respectively)		

<p>ly processa ble dataset</p>			<p>About 100 instruments in NRT (Mini-MPL, CHM15k from E-PROFILE) since the beginning of the year 2022</p>		
<p>Referenc es, validatio n exercises</p>	<p>Wiegner et al., 2014, https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-7-1979-2014 Dionisi et al, 2018, https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-11-6013-2018 Diémoz et al., 2019, https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-3065-2019 Diémoz et al., 2019, https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-10129-2019 Diémoz et al., 2020, https://www.alice-net.eu/documents/Alice-net-Vprofiles_AOD_comparison_technote-20200616.pdf Bellini et al., 2022, https://www.alice-net.eu/documents/Alice-netEGU22.pdf</p>	<p>Tesche et al. 2009 JGR https://doi.org/10.1029/2009JD011862 Ansmann et al. 2011 JGR https://doi.org/10.1029/2010JD015567 Osborne et al.,2019, https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-3557-2019 Osborne et al, 2022, https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-2975-2022</p>	<p>A-Profiles retrievals are based on BASIC, used in the following publications: - Mortier et al., 2013 - Bovchaliuk et al., 2016 - Derimian et al., 2012 - Karol et al., 2013 - Mortier et al., 2016 - Popovici et al., 2018 - Mortier et al., 2012</p> <p>Some comparisons: - Validation exercises</p>	<p>Popovici et al., 2018 Popovici et al., 2022 Mortier et al., 2013</p>	